

Transfer hydrogenation of cellulose based oligomers over carbon supported Ru catalyst in a fixed bed reactor

Abhijit Shrotri,^[a] Hirokazu Kobayashi,^[b] Akshat Tanksale,^[c] Atsushi Fukuoka,^[b] and Jorge Beltramini*^[a]

Ru/C was found to be active for transfer hydrogenation of cellulose oligomers which were produced by the milling of acidulated microcrystalline cellulose. C₆ sugar alcohol yield of 85 % was obtained in less than 1 h reaction time in a batch reactor. Optimum reaction conditions for transfer hydrogenation were determined as 180 °C and a pH above 2.2 using glucose as a substrate. Use of deuterium as a marker established that direct transfer of hydride

species from iso-propanol to glucose takes place through the di-hydride mechanism. Formation of molecular H₂ from iso-propanol dehydrogenation was found to be a side reaction with little influence on the glucose hydrogenation step. Conversion of cellulose oligomers into hexitols was also successfully achieved in a fixed bed continuous flow reactor with 36.4% yield at LHSV of 4,7 h⁻¹. The activity of catalyst did not decline even after 12 h of on-stream reaction.

1.0 Introduction

Liquid hydrocarbon fossil fuels are soon expected to be economically unfavourable due to high demand and shortage of supply.^[1] The global transport sector fuel demand, as of 2010, was 2,200 million metric tons of oil equivalents,^[2] biofuels accounted for only 2.3 % of this total demand.^[3] To fulfil future demands, a sustainable technology needs to be developed which can facilitate the economic production of carbon based fuels.^[4] Carbohydrates derived from biomass are widely viewed as a sustainable raw material for the production of carbon based liquid fuels in the future.^[5] Cellulose is of particular interest as it is the most abundant carbohydrate on Earth and is not part of the human food supply.^[6-7] Cellulose is a homopolymer composed only of glucose monomer units, a characteristic that allows a high yield of selective products. Cellulose can be depolymerised into glucose and then converted to a variety of platform chemicals such as sugar alcohols.^[8] Conversion of cellulose to C₆ sugar alcohols is achieved through successive hydrolysis and hydrogenation reactions in an aqueous medium.^[9] These sugar alcohols can then be used as a precursor for biofuels and various other chemicals.

Conversion of cellulose to C₆ sugar alcohols (hexitols) in a single pot reaction using supported Pt and Ru catalyst under H₂ pressure was first reported in 2006.^[10] Various other catalysts have since been reported to convert cellulose to hexitols.^[11-14] The process involves a two-step reaction where cellulose is first converted to glucose through hydrolysis.^[15] The rate of hydrolysis is promoted by the presence of metal catalyst as well as hot compressed water.^[16] Alternatively, mineral and organic acid can also be added to further promote the hydrolysis reaction.^[17] In the second step, glucose undergoes hydrogenation over the metal surface to produce hexitols. Hydrolysis is the rate limiting step in this process as the hydrogenation reaction is relatively fast.^[11] Increasing the rate of hydrolysis holds the key towards industrial implementation of this process.

Liquid hydrocarbon fuels produced through hexitols can be a major contributor to total biofuel production. However, the technology is currently under development and there are many challenges yet to be solved before industrial scale production of hexitols can be achieved. Currently this reaction is studied only at laboratory scale batch reactors, which are convenient for small-scale research and manufacturing of pharmaceutical drugs. A continuous reactor system is more suited for the large-scale production of hexitols from cellulosic biomass. Apart from being cost effective and easily scalable, continuous processes also offer improved energy efficiency, safety, and process control.^[18] The use of a continuous reactor for hexitol production is hindered by unique challenges such as the insolubility of cellulose in water and the use of high-pressure hydrogen. These issues cannot be resolved by engineering solutions alone and alternative reaction pathways must be investigated to develop an easily scalable continuous process.

As previously mentioned, one of the issues associated with the scale up of this process is the need for high-pressure hydrogen to achieve a fast hydrogenation rate. Excess hydrogen at high pressure is required to reduce degradation of glucose under the hydrothermal reaction conditions required for cellulose hydrolysis. Hydrogen pressure in excess of 40 bar is needed to achieve maximum selectivity for the hydrogenation of glucose.^[19]

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- [a] *Dr J. Beltramini, A. Shrotri*
ARC Centre of Excellence for Functional Nanomaterials
University of Queensland
St Lucia, QLD, 4072, Australia
Fax: (+61 7 3346 3973)
E-mail: j.beltramini@uq.edu.au
- [b] *Prof A. Fukuoka, Dr H. Kobayashi*
Catalysis Research Centre
Hokkaido University
Kita 21 Nishi 10, Kita Ku, Sapporo, 001-0021, Japan
- [c] *Dr A. Tanksale*
Department of Chemical Engineering
Monash University
Clayton, VIC 3800, Australia

Apart from being a safety hazard, high-pressure hydrogen increases the capital cost of reaction vessels. Furthermore, a headspace of pressurised hydrogen is needed to maintain equilibrium solubility as hydrogen is consumed during the reaction. This prohibits the use of a continuous flow fixed bed reactor. Recently a method to convert cellulose into hexitols by transfer hydrogenation using carbon supported Ru catalyst in the presence of iso-propanol was reported.^[20] Hydrogen required for the reaction was produced in situ by dehydrogenation of iso-propanol (Scheme 1). Carbon supported Ru catalyst simultaneously catalysed the dehydrogenation of iso-propanol and hydrogenation of glucose. Hexitol yield of 46.9 % was reported using Ru supported on activated carbon after 18 h of reaction. As no hydrogen pressure was required and a relatively cheap hydrogen precursor was used, we believe this could be a promising route for economic production of hexitols. However, the limitation of this report was the long reaction time of 18 h. The authors used ball milled amorphous cellulose instead of crystalline cellulose to increase rate of hydrolysis, but despite that the reaction time was very long. Furthermore, the mechanism of hydrogen transfer from iso-propanol to glucose is still unknown. The significance of H₂ generated by iso-propanol dehydrogenation, which creates overhead H₂ gas pressure during the reaction is also not clearly understood.

Scheme 1. Sequential hydrolysis and transfer hydrogenation of cellulose over carbon supported Ru catalyst using iso-propanol as hydrogen donor to produce hexitols (adapted from ^[20]).

Reaction time required for conversion of cellulose into Hexitol can be reduced by increasing the reactivity of cellulose. The ordered crystalline structure of cellulose makes it insoluble in water and other conventional solvents.^[21] The crystalline structure and the insolubility of cellulose in water limits access to the β (1→4) glycoside bonds linking the individual monomer units.^[22] Pre-treatment methods such as ball milling is reported to be effective in reducing the degree of crystallinity and increasing the yield of hydrolysis products^[23]. Nevertheless amorphous cellulose produced after pre-treatment is also insoluble in water leading to long reaction times. Moreover use of solid cellulose at commercial scale would require a slurry reactor which is difficult to design and operate due to clogging problems. Recently, mechanocatalytic treatment for depolymerisation of acidulated cellulose was reported as a successful method to produce water-soluble oligomers.^[24-25] The oligomers were highly reactive compared to solid cellulose and hexitol yield of more than 90% was achieved with only 1 h of reaction time using a bimetallic Ni-Pt catalyst.^[24] Therefore, use of soluble cellulose oligomers can

be an effective method to reduce reaction time. It would also enable using a fixed bed reactor for continuous production of hexitols.

In this paper, we investigate in detail the transfer hydrogenation of cellulose in a batch reactor with an objective to identify optimum temperature and feed ratio for conducting the reaction in a fixed bed reactor. We identify the optimum reaction conditions suitable for both hydrolysis and hydrogenation reactions. The pathway of hydrogen transfer from iso-propanol to glucose is also determined to ascertain the influence of overhead hydrogen pressure. Finally, we demonstrate the feasibility of producing hexitols from cellulose in a continuous flow fixed bed reactor.

2.0 Results and Discussion

2.1 Catalyst characterisation

The catalyst support used for the transfer hydrogenation reaction was Norit SX Ultra activated charcoal powder purchased from Sigma Aldrich. This support was chosen for its superior performance in transfer hydrogenation of cellulose.^[20] Catalyst was prepared by loading the support with 2 wt% Ru using ruthenium (III) nitrosyl nitrate as a precursor. The catalyst was reduced under H₂ flow prior to reaction and referred as Ru/AC(N) hereafter. The BET surface area of support was 1210 m²/g, which reduced to 1150 m²/g after impregnation with Ru metal. The average metal particle size was 1.4 nm as observed in the TEM image (Figure 1). The dispersion of Ru on the catalyst was calculated to be 25.8% using CO chemisorption. Therefore, Ru was found to be well dispersed on the carbon support with fairly uniform particle size. Ru is known to be present in its trivalent and tetravalent form as it quickly oxidises in the presence of air to RuO₂·2H₂O at room temperature before the reaction^[20]. Recently it was reported that the RuO₂·2H₂O is reduced to Ru metal in the presence of iso-propanol during the reaction, and the metallic Ru particles formed act as the active catalyst species.^[26]

Figure 1. TEM image of 2 wt% Ru/AC(N) along with particle size distribution

2.2 Effect of temperature, pH and feed ratio on transfer hydrogenation of glucose

Yield of hexitol from transfer hydrogenation is limited by the slow rate of cellulose hydrolysis. Faster hydrolysis can be achieved by increasing the reaction temperature or reducing the solution pH. However, under severe conditions, the rate of glucose

degradation is also accelerated and an optimum reaction condition must be established to maximise yield of hexitols. The reaction conditions for the efficient transfer hydrogenation of glucose using Ru/AC(N) were first investigated at different temperatures without the addition of any acid, resulting in a measured pH of 5.3. Hexitol yield changed significantly within the temperature range of 170-200 °C (Figure 2A). After 20 min of reaction the glucose conversion was 75% and 82%, along with a hexitol yield of 73.6% and 79.7% at 170 °C and 180 °C respectively. At higher temperatures the yield and conversion were both lower. Possible factors for lower yield at higher temperature could be lower solubility of hydrogen produced by dehydrogenation of iso-propanol, deactivation of catalyst and degradation of glucose.^[27]

Using glucose as the feedstock we found that the optimum temperature for transfer hydrogenation was 180 °C. However, hydrolysis of cellulose is very slow at this temperature in the absence of mineral acids. Therefore, we tested the effect of pH on transfer hydrogenation of glucose because it is well known that cellulose hydrolysis is accelerated at low pH. Furthermore, the oligomers used in section 2.3 of the discussion contain a small amount of sulphuric acid, which leads to the formation of a mildly acidic reaction mixture of pH 2-3. As such, an equivalent amount of acid present in the oligomers (0.25 mmol H₂SO₄ per g of oligomers) was added to the glucose mixture, which resulted in a pH of 2.4 before the reaction. Lowering the pH from 5.3 (no acid) to 2.4 gave higher conversion of glucose at 180 °C and 190 °C (Figure 2B). However, the yield of hexitol did not increase accordingly due to an increase in degradation of glucose. Lowering the pH further to 2.2 by increasing the acid amount to 0.5 mmol significantly lowered the yield of hexitol at all temperatures (Figure 2C). These results suggest that, as the severity of reaction increases with increased acid concentration or temperature, the catalyst is deactivated reducing yield of hexitol, presumably due to the adsorption of glucose degradation products on the catalyst surface.

Another important factor affecting the rate of transfer hydrogenation was found to be the ratio of water to iso-propanol in the feed. Changes in this ratio affects the transfer hydrogenation reaction by changing the solubility of hydrogen, the thermodynamic interaction of solvent with the reactants and products, and the competitive adsorption of iso-propanol vs glucose on the catalyst surface.^[28] Increasing iso-propanol is known to reduce the rate of hydrogenation under conventional hydrogenation methods.^[29] During transfer hydrogenation of glucose in the presence of Ru/AC(N) at 180 °C, we observed a hexitol yield of 68.5% with 25%(vol) iso-propanol, which increased to 79.7% with 50%(vol) iso-propanol. Further increasing the iso-propanol amount to 75%(vol) reduced the hexitol yield to 29.8%.

2.3 Transfer hydrogenation of cellulose oligomers

Optimised conditions for glucose transfer hydrogenation (pH = 2.4, water to iso-propanol vol ratio 1:1) were tested for transfer

Figure 2. Transfer hydrogenation of glucose to hexitols in batch reactor. Glucose conversion (●) and yield of hexitols (bars) at (A) pH 5.3, (B) pH 2.4, and (C) pH 2.2. Reaction conditions: 324 mg glucose, Ru/AC(N) catalyst 100 mg (metal 2 wt%), water 20 mL, 2-propanol 20 mL, 15 bar Ar at room temperature, 20 min.

hydrogenation of cellulose oligomers at different temperatures. These oligomers were produced by milling cellulose impregnated with sulphuric acid, which resulted in the rapid depolymerisation of the polymer chain. A completely soluble substrate was obtained when cellulose impregnated with 0.25 mmol of H₂SO₄/g was milled for 10 h. An earlier study of these soluble oligomers had revealed that the soluble oligomers have an average degree of polymerisation of 5 to 6 monomer units. A fraction of these monomers are linked via α (1→6) linkages, which along with other factors, resulted in instant solubility of the oligomers in water despite their high degree of polymerisation.^[24] However, the solubility of oligomers in the reaction mixture will be affected by the presence of iso-propanol. The oligomers were not completely

soluble in 50% (vol) iso-propanol solution at room temperature and instead a cloudy solution was obtained.

Conversion of cellulose oligomers to hexitols through transfer hydrogenation at various temperatures is shown in Figure 3. After 20 min reaction, the highest yield of hexitols (35.3%) was obtained at 180 °C. When temperature is lowered to 170 °C lower yield of 22.2% was observed, which was likely due to lower hydrolysis of oligomers and also due to a slow hydrogenation. As observed in section 2.2, glucose hydrogenation is not favoured at higher temperature. This resulted in high amount of glucose in the product at 190 °C and 200 °C because hydrolysis of oligomers was favoured but hydrogenation of glucose was slow. Upon increasing the reaction time to 40 min, hexitol yield increased to 77.5% at 180 °C and a maximum yield of 83.4% was obtained after 1 h of reaction.

Figure 3. Yield of products from transfer hydrogenation of cellulose oligomers in batch reactor. Reaction conditions: 324 mg cellulose oligomers, Ru/AC(N) catalyst 100 mg (metal 2 wt%), water 20 mL, iso-propanol 20 mL, pH = 2.4, 15 bar Ar at room temperature, 20 min.

2.4 Mechanism of hydrogen transfer

During transfer hydrogenation experiments it was observed that after the reaction temperature was reached, the pressure of the reactor gradually increased by 3-5 bar. Even after the reactor was cooled to room temperature, increased pressure of 3-5 bar was maintained, indicating that a gaseous product was generated. Using gas chromatography this gaseous product was identified as H₂ gas, which was likely produced through dehydrogenation of iso-propanol. In an earlier publication Ru/AC(N) was found to be active for hydrogenation under 8 bar H₂ pressure as well as under transfer hydrogenation conditions where 8 bar H₂ was produced by dehydrogenation of iso-propanol^[20]. In a fixed bed reactor this overhead space is not available and H₂ gas formed would quickly leave the system. Hence it is imperative to determine the role of overhead H₂ pressure in this reaction.

It is unlikely that such a low partial pressure of H₂ may produce the high rates of hydrogenation observed in our results. Low partial pressure of hydrogen would result in very low solubility of hydrogen, thereby limiting the adsorption of hydrogen

over the catalyst surface. As a result, the influence of molecular H₂ in our reaction was investigated by repeating the reaction in the presence of H₂ gas. To simulate the solvent effect of iso-propanol during transfer hydrogenation, an equivalent amount of n-propanol was used which does not undergo dehydrogenation to produce H₂. In comparison to 79.5% yield of hexitols during transfer hydrogenation at 180 °C, only 2.9% hexitols was obtained with 5 bar H₂ partial pressure in the presence of n-propanol. Increasing the pressure of H₂ to 15 bar increased the yield to 11.9 % which was still substantially lower compared to the yield obtained during transfer hydrogenation. Based on these observations we conclude that it is unlikely for the reaction to proceed through the formation of H₂ gas, and the influence of H₂ gas pressure is minimal on the rate of hydrogenation.

Adsorbed hydrogen species on the surface of the catalyst, which is produced by dehydrogenation of iso-propanol could be directly transferred on to the adsorbed glucose molecule. The mechanism of such direct transfer of hydrogen using homogenous Ru complex catalysts has been extensively investigated^[30]. However, the heterogeneous transfer hydrogenation mechanism is not very well understood. To establish the source of hydrogen that is taking part in the hydrogenation reaction we performed two experiments using deuterium instead of hydrogen in the form of D₂ and D₂O. The sorbitol product obtained from these reactions can be isolated and analysed using proton NMR spectroscopy. Deuterium is inactive towards magnetisation during NMR, and can serve as a marker to determine the source of hydrogen taking part in the reaction. Therefore, the presence of deuterium attached to the carbon atom of sorbitol will lead to an absence of corresponding proton peak in the NMR spectrum. Hydrogenation of glucose adds one H atoms to the carbonyl oxygen and one to the anomeric carbon.^[31] The latter H atom is observed in the proton NMR spectrum at position H1 and H1' (Figure 4). Doublets

Figure 4. Proton NMR spectrum of sorbitol dissolved in D₂O at 298 K. (i) sorbitol standard, (ii) sorbitol obtained after reaction in the presence of H₂O, iso-propanol and D₂, (iii) sorbitol obtained after reaction in the presence of D₂O, iso-propanol and H₂

centred at a chemical shift of 3.63 ppm and 3.72 ppm represent the position H1 and H1' in the NMR spectrum.^[32] Due to overlap of multiple peaks it is not possible to evaluate the area for individual protons. However, a relative reduction in the peak can be calculated by dividing the spectrum into three sections such that there is no overlap of peaks between adjacent sections. When integrating individual sections, the ratio of area was found to be 3.00 : 2.05 : 3.02 for sections a, b and c respectively for a standard sorbitol sample. This observed ratio is in accordance with the expected theoretical ratio of 3 : 2 : 3.

In experiment 1 hydrogenation of glucose was carried out in the presence of iso-propanol, H₂O and 5 bar D₂ (scheme 2a). In the proton NMR spectrum of sorbitol product all proton peaks were clearly observed despite a lower resolution due to a limited amount of sample obtained through HPLC (Figure 4, spectrum ii). The area ratio was 3.00 : 1.99 : 3.05 for sections a, b, and c respectively. As the ratio is same as the standard spectrum we can infer that D was not present on positions at H1 and H1'. In experiment 2 the reaction was performed in the presence of iso-propanol, D₂O and 5 bar H₂ (Scheme 2b). Under this condition the proton attached to the hydroxyl group in iso-propanol would quickly exchange with deuterium. This deuterium would then participate in the hydrogenation of glucose. In the proton NMR spectra for sorbitol obtained from this reaction a clear reduction in peak intensities for H1 and H1' is observed at a chemical shift of 3.63 and 3.72 ppm (Fig 4 spectrum iii). The ratio of areas in this case was 3.00 : 1.62 : 2.72 for section a, b and c respectively. The reduction in area corresponds to 66% of sorbitol molecules with D attached to its carbon atom. These results support the di-hydride mechanism where both the hydrogen atoms are transferred to the metal surface losing their identity.^[33] The reduction in area was higher than the predicted 50% when hydroxyl hydrogen in all iso-propanol molecules is replaced by deuterium. Increased presence of deuterium can be attributed to dissociative adsorption of deuterated water over Ru surface, forming surface hydroxyl intermediates and protons, which can take part in the reaction^[34]. In summary, these findings confirm that the primary source of hydrogen for hydrogenation is through direct transfer of adsorbed hydrogen species from iso-propanol to glucose over the Ru surface. NMR results further confirm that gaseous H₂ formed as a by-product of dehydrogenation reaction did not take part in the hydrogenation of glucose.

Scheme 2. Experiments showing use of deuterium as a marker to identify source of hydrogen taking part in glucose hydrogenation (a) Use of D₂ gas did not show any presence of deuterated sorbitol. (b) In presence of D₂O, deuterated iso-propanol was formed which led to formation of deuterated sorbitol

2.5 Transfer hydrogenation of glucose and cellulose oligomers in the fixed bed reactor system

A major advantage of using soluble cellulose oligomers for transfer hydrogenation reaction is the ability to perform the reaction in a fixed bed continuous reactor. The process is further simplified, as overhead H₂ pressure is not required for transfer hydrogenation as concluded from the NMR results. A simple U shaped fixed bed reactor was designed using 1/4" OD stainless steel Swagelok tube. Liquid feed was pumped into the reactor at a steady flow using an HPLC pump. The system was pressurised to 60 bar by using a back pressure regulator. This prevented vaporisation of liquids at reaction temperatures. Once the required pressure was reached and the flow was steady the reactor was dipped in a stirred oil bath maintained at the reaction temperature. It is important to note that effects due to mass and heat transfer cannot be ignored in such a simple system, and therefore an attempt to evaluate kinetics of the reaction was not made. Furthermore, due to back mixing of liquid in the pressure regulator, which has a substantially high volume compared to the reactor, an induction phase in the first 50 mins was observed. Efficiency of the reaction was calculated in terms of liquid hourly space velocity (LHSV), defined here as the ratio of volumetric flow rate of feed solution (ml h⁻¹) and the heated volume of reactor (ml). The space velocity was calculated in terms of reactor volume instead of catalyst mass because the rate-limiting hydrolysis reaction is not catalysed by the Ru catalyst.

Glucose solution was initially used as a feed to test the feasibility of transfer hydrogenation in a fixed bed reactor. A small reactor with a heated volume of 0.95 ml was loaded with 250 mg reduced Ru/AC(N) resulting in a catalyst to reactor volume ratio of 263 mg/ml. As shown in Figure 5, high yield of hexitols was obtained at liquid flow rates between 0.2-0.4 ml min⁻¹, which corresponds to LHSV of 12.6-25.2 h⁻¹. Significantly high hexitol yields were obtained despite a short residence time in the reactor. Highest hexitol yield of 75.9% was obtained at LHSV of 18.9 h⁻¹. The selectivity for hexitols was 66.0%, 77.5 % and 85.1 % for LHSV of 12.6 h⁻¹, 18.9 h⁻¹ and 25.2 h⁻¹. A lower selectivity

Figure 5. Yield of hexitols obtained at different flow rate in a fixed bed reactor of heated volume 0.95 ml. LHSV 12.6 ●, LHSV 18.9 ▼ and LHSV 25.2 ■. Reaction conditions: Feed concentration of 8.1 mg/ml glucose in 50%(vol) iso-propanol in water, 2wt% Ru/AC(N) (263 mg catalyst/ml of heated volume), reaction temperature 180 °C, system pressure 60 bar.

compared to the batch reactor was presumably due to the presence of non-catalytic heated zone inside the reactor where glucose would degrade. This is also the cause of increase in selectivity at higher LHSV when the residence time is lowered. The molar ratio of acetone produced to hexitols yield was 20.1, 12.8 and 10.6 respectively, indicating better efficiency of hydrogen transfer at higher LHSV. H₂ gas was produced during the reaction, which travelled through the system under biphasic flow before exiting through the pressure regulator.

Glucose solution was later replaced with cellulose oligomer solution as the feed for sequential hydrolysis and hydrogenation in the fixed bed reactor. As mentioned earlier in section 2.3 the oligomers were not completely soluble in 50% (vol) iso-propanol solution at room temperature. Therefore, to operate the continuous reactor the feed was prepared using 25% (vol) iso-propanol in water with a pH of 2.7. Using the 0.95 ml heated volume reactor with 250 mg catalyst and LHSV of 18.9 h⁻¹ a hexitol yield of 18.7% was obtained (Figure 6). The low hexitol yield was attributed to the incomplete conversion of oligomers to glucose due to very small residence time. Increasing the catalyst loading to 370 mg/ml did not have any significant effect resulting in hexitol yield of only 19.7 % (result not shown in the graph). This further confirms that the hydrolysis of oligomers is the limiting reaction in fixed bed reaction conditions. To promote the hydrolysis of oligomers the residence time was increased by increasing reactor volume, keeping the flow rate constant at 0.3 ml min⁻¹ and thereby reducing the LHSV. The catalyst loading was also kept constant at 263 mg/ml. Hexitol yield increased to 26.2 % with LHSV of 9.5 h⁻¹. Further decreasing the LHSV to 4.7 h⁻¹ increased the hexitol yield to 32.7 %. This shows that the only limiting factor in this process is the incomplete hydrolysis, which can be eliminated by increasing the residence time of the reactant. Finally to increase the efficiency of the process, feed concentration was increased to 16.2 mg/ml of cellulose oligomers. The pH of the solution also decreased to 2.35 with higher concentration of H₂SO₄. Hexitol yield of 36.4% was obtained at a LHSV of 4.7 h⁻¹. Higher hexitol yield was due to the increased rate of hydrolysis at lower pH. This reaction was performed for over 12 h on stream and the catalytic activity did not decline

Figure 6. Yield of hexitols from transfer hydrogenation of cellulose oligomers in fixed bed reactor of different volume at a flow rate of 0.3 ml min⁻¹. LHSV 18.9 ●, LHSV 9.5 ▼, and LHSV 4.7 ■. Reaction conditions: feed 8.1 mg/ml cellulose oligomers in 25% (vol) iso-propanol in water, 2wt % Ru/AC(N) 263 mg/ml, 180 °C, flow 0.3 ml min⁻¹, system pressure 60 bar, pH 2.7

during this period, suggesting that the catalyst was highly stable for continuous operation.

3.0 Conclusions

Ru supported on an activated carbon catalyst was prepared for transfer hydrogenation. High dispersion of Ru was obtained leading to high hexitol yields. The rate of glucose hydrogenation was found to be dependent on temperature with maximum hexitol yield obtained at 180 °C. Other influencing factors were presence of acids and amount of iso-propanol present. It was shown that the H₂ gas produced by dehydrogenation of iso-propanol played negligible role in the hydrogenation reaction due to low H₂ partial pressure. Direct transfer of hydrogen from iso-propanol to glucose was proven through the di-hydride mechanism without the participation of molecular H₂. The transfer hydrogenation process was effective for the direct conversion of cellulose oligomers to hexitols. A maximum yield of 83.4% hexitols was obtained in a batch reactor, which is the highest reported yield of hexitols from cellulose without using molecular H₂. This process was efficiently carried out in a fixed bed reactor. Maximum hexitol yield of 36.4 % was obtained at a LHSV of 4.7 h⁻¹ and no apparent deactivation of the catalyst was observed over 12 h run. Yield of hexitols was limited by the extent of oligomer hydrolysis, which can be increasing by increasing the retention time. These results increase the viability of economical manufacturing of hexitols from cellulose at large scale. Further work to improve this process is now focused towards reducing the formation of H₂ gas, increasing the efficiency of hydrogen transfer, and identifying the reaction kinetics in the fixed bed reactor.

4.0 Experimental

4.1 Catalyst Preparation and Characterisation

Norit SX Ultra activated charcoal and Ruthenium nitrosyl nitrate solution (1.5 wt% Ru) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. 2wt % Ru catalyst was prepared using the conventional impregnation method. Required amount of ruthenium(III) nitrosyl nitrate solution was added drop-wise to 1g of carbon support dispersed in 10 ml of water. The mixture was diluted to a total volume of 25 ml and then stirred for 16 h at room temperature. After stirring the water was removed using rotary evaporator and the catalyst was then dried under vacuum for 18 h. The dried catalyst was then reduced under H₂ flow (30 ml min⁻¹) for 2 h at 400 °C. Surface area and pore size of catalyst was measured by N₂ physisorption using a Belsorb-Mini II instrument at 77 K. Metal surface area was measured by dynamic CO chemisorption performed on a Belcat-A instrument using a TCD detector. Prior to CO pulse adsorption the catalyst was reduced at 400 °C for 2 h followed by purging with He at 400 °C for 1 h before cooling to 30 °C under He flow. TEM images were taken using a JEOL 2100 microscope operating at 200 KV.

4.2 Cellulose depolymerisation

Water soluble cellulose based oligomers were produced using methods described elsewhere^[24]. In a typical method, 2.5 mmol of H₂SO₄ was diluted in 25 ml volume. 10g of Sigmacell micro-crystalline cellulose (Aldrich) was then added to this solution and stirred for a few minutes. The resulting slurry was dried using a rotary evaporator followed by overnight air-drying at 50 °C. The acidulated cellulose powder thus obtained was then milled in a planetary ball mill with a cellulose to ball weight ratio of 1:10 using 5 mm stainless steel balls. The mill was operated at 300 rpm, with a 20 min pause after every 15 minutes of continuous milling. Intermittent milling was performed to

avoid overheating of reactants due to the heat generated during milling.

4.3 Catalytic Reactions

Catalytic batch reactions were performed using a haste alloy C22 batch reactor supplied by OM-Lab Tech, Japan. The reactor was charged with 324 mg of substrate along with 100 mg of catalyst and 40ml of water/iso-propanol mixture. The reactor was purged to remove air and then pressurised with Ar at 15 bar before heating. After the reaction was complete the catalyst was separated by centrifugation and the solution was analysed using HPLC.

Continuous fixed bed reactions were performed on a custom built reaction system. An Alltech HPLC pump was used for feeding the liquid into the fixed bed reactor. The U shaped fixed bed reactors were made using 1/4" OD SS316 Swagelok tubing. Reduced catalyst was loaded into the reactor and a small amount of quartz wool was inserted from both sides of the reactor to hold the catalyst in place. A 7 micron Swagelok inline filter was connected to the reactor exit which was followed by a Swagelok back pressure regulator. A steady flow was established through the system until the desired pressure was achieved. The reactor was then slowly dipped into a stirred oil bath set at the reaction temperature; at this moment the reaction time was noted as 0 min.

Liquid products were analysed using a Shimadzu HPLC system equipped with Rezex RPM/RCM monosaccharide columns, with a mobile phase flow rate of 0.6 ml min⁻¹. The products were detected using a Refractive index detector and a Shimadzu ELSDII detector operating at 30 °C.

4.4 NMR analysis

Sorbitol product for NMR analysis was obtained by isolating it from the reaction mixture using HPLC. After about 15 repetitions the collected sorbitol solution was dried to remove water and subsequently dissolved in D₂O for NMR analysis. Proton NMR spectra of sorbitol solution was obtained using a JEOL JNM-ECP400 spectrometer operating at 400 MHz using a pulse repetition time of 1 s with 64 scans. The obtained spectrum was referenced externally to DSS (4,4-dimethyl-4-silapentane-1-sulfonic acid).

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Keywords: Biomass • cellulose • Transfer hydrogenation • platform chemicals • Fixed bed reactor

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FULL PAPER

*Abhijit Shrotri, Hirokazu Kobayashi,
Akshat Tanksale, Atsushi Fukuoka, and
Jorge Beltramini**

**Title: Transfer hydrogenation of
cellulose based oligomers over
carbon supported Ru catalyst in a
fixed bed reactor**

Fix that bed: First demonstration of catalytic conversion of cellulose to sugar alcohols with high yield in a fixed bed continuous reactor through hydrolytic transfer hydrogenation. Ru supported on carbon catalyses direct hydrogen transfer from iso-propanol to glucose without involvement of H_2 gas.